

Collatz with a twist

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Let q be the set of the first ten primes:

```
q = [2 3 5 7 11 13 17 19 23 29]
```

and run the following OCTAVE/MATLAB loop on this set using the standard Collatz function followed by a 'remove evens' command until the set is whittled down to just one element:

```
q=.5*(3*q+1);  
% Remove evens  
id=q-2*(floor(q/2));  
q=nonzeros(q.*id);
```

The last number standing here is 6.31011962890625.

This routine was run over a set of consecutive primes using increasing upper bounds of multiple powers-of-ten (up to 10,000,000,000), or 455,052,511 primes; thus the 'primes' search in OCTAVE used was

```
q = primes(n*10k), n = 1, 2, ..., 9 for each k = 1, 2, ..., 9.
```

At most 30 iterations were needed to reach a limit here. The image below plots each limit number as the prime count increased.

While the resulting step function is apparent and convergence seemed likely at intermediate stages, it was not to be, at least for the limited number of primes tested here. Only sixteen of the limits reached were actually unique; these were (to four decimals):

2.7885	6.3101	6.8644	11.4361	11.4982
18.7662	29.2021	31.3547	56.0172	77.8998

A very different picture emerged when the 'floor' function was replaced by the 'ceiling' command in the same loop; see the plotted results below.

While convergence still did not happen, the variation in limits is obviously far smaller.

It is interesting to compare limits for the first 10 primes using Collatz functions

$$C_p(t) = (pt + 1)/2, \text{ for } p = 3, 5, 7, \text{ and } 11$$

for both 'floor' and 'ceiling' roundoffs; see the table below.

	C_3	C_5	C_7	C_{11}
ffloor	6.310	344.107	840.552	23596.169
ceiling	-0.090	-9.867	2047.756	203.144

A few passes using non-prime weights yielded no limits at all.

Finally, the availability of a rather large sequence of consecutive primes sampled at the upper bound increments listed above, allowed a comparison of the PNT counter

$$n/\ln(n)$$

with Chebyshev's estimate

$$n/\ln(n/e) = n/(\ln(n)-1)$$

Percent error rates are plotted below; top tier PNT, bottom tier Chebyshev. Hmm!

